

REINCARNATE

Autonomous robotic system for on-site waste assessment and separation: Wuhan Demonstration Case

Innovation + Demo Case

Technical Deep-Dive Report

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Reincarnate project

The average lifespan of a building is 39 years — in Europe, it is only 25-30 years — and the main reason for demolition is obsolescence. This is why there is a large amount of construction and demolition waste (CDW) — representing approximately 25-30% of all waste in Europe —, in addition to that generated in current construction works.

The recycling rate for CDW is relatively high (above 75%). This activity generated \$126.89 billion in 2019 — Europe contributed the largest share, almost two-fifths of the total global market — and is projected to reach \$149.19 billion by 2027. Unfortunately, many of the most valuable materials in CDW cannot be meaningfully separated and end up in landfills.

This helps to get an idea of the efficiency potential for climate neutrality that exists in construction.

Reincarnate aims at advancing circular economy practices within the European construction industry and enabling to significantly maximise the life cycle of buildings, construction products and materials, reduce CDW by 80%, increase the reusability of buildings, construction products and materials and, as a result, lower the sector's emissions by 70%.

As a result of these actions, Reincarnate will significantly advance circular economy practices within the European construction industry.

First, it will create a Circular Potential Information Management (CP-IM) platform and a set of innovations to use it. These solutions will draw upon emerging digital technologies, such as digital twin representation, artificial intelligence, and robotic automation.

3 empirically proven social science insights will allow fostering widespread adoption of reused high-quality construction products and materials, and business eco-system development frameworks to combine actors within sustainable value chains.

All innovations will be demonstrated on eleven selected real-world projects and value chains. Furthermore, business process guidelines and an e-learning platform will be developed to drive the dissemination and exploitation of the Reincarnate results.

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1. Executive summary

This report presents an autonomous robotic system developed for on-site construction waste assessment and separation within the REINCARNATE project framework. The demonstration focuses on the Longhu Binjiang Tianjie construction site in Wuhan, China, where the system is deployed to support automated identification and handling of construction and demolition waste (CDW). Traditional waste sorting methods in construction environments often rely on manual labor, which can be inefficient and potentially hazardous[1].

The proposed robotic system integrates a mobile platform, a lightweight six-degree-of-freedom robotic arm, and a multi-modal perception system combining LiDAR sensing, RGB-D stereo vision, and artificial intelligence-based recognition algorithms[2]. Waste objects are detected using a YOLOv8-based visual detection pipeline and localized through point cloud processing to estimate their three-dimensional positions[3]. The robot can then perform automated grasping and sorting operations using a force-adaptive manipulation strategy[4].

The demonstration results show that the system can effectively support automated waste inspection and handling in semi-structured construction environments. By integrating robotic perception, navigation, and manipulation technologies, the solution contributes to improved construction waste management efficiency, reduced manual labor requirements, and enhanced safety conditions. The system also supports the REINCARNATE objectives of digital waste monitoring and circular construction practices.

2. Context and objectives

The construction and demolition (C&D) sector represents one of the largest sources of solid waste worldwide[1]. With the rapid pace of urbanization and infrastructure development, the generation of construction and demolition waste (CDW) has increased significantly in recent decades. Materials such as concrete, bricks, wood, plastics, and metals are frequently discarded during building construction, renovation, and demolition processes. Although many of these materials have the potential to be recycled or reused, they are often disposed of as mixed waste due to the lack of efficient sorting and assessment mechanisms at construction sites[1]. As a result, valuable resources are lost, and the environmental burden associated with landfill disposal continues to grow.

Traditional construction waste management practices typically rely on manual inspection, classification, and transportation of waste materials. Workers manually identify different waste types and sort them into separate categories before sending them to recycling facilities or disposal sites. While this approach is widely used, it presents several limitations. Manual sorting is labor-intensive and time-consuming, and it may expose workers to hazardous materials, dust, and unsafe working conditions[5]. In addition, the increasing complexity of construction sites and the diversity of waste materials make it difficult to maintain consistent sorting accuracy using purely manual methods.

Figure 1. Manually picking up construction waste

To address these challenges, emerging digital and robotic technologies have begun to play an important role in construction waste management[6]. Advances in robotics, artificial intelligence, and sensing technologies have enabled the development of automated systems capable of perceiving complex environments, identifying materials, and performing manipulation tasks[7]. Autonomous robotic platforms equipped with multi-modal perception systems can collect environmental data, detect objects, and interact with physical materials in real time[8]. These technologies provide new opportunities to improve efficiency, safety, and sustainability in construction waste management.

Within the framework of the REINCARNATE project, this demonstration explores the application of an autonomous robotic system for on-site construction waste assessment and separation. The proposed system integrates a mobile robotic platform, multi-sensor perception technologies, and intelligent recognition algorithms to enable automated detection, localization, and handling of waste materials directly at construction sites[6]. The demonstration was conducted at the Longhu Binjiang Tianjie construction project in Wuhan, China, which represents a typical semi-structured construction environment with diverse materials, dynamic conditions, and spatial constraints.

Figure 2. Robotic autonomous picking

The robotic system is designed to perform several key functions. First, it can navigate autonomously within the construction site using LiDAR-based mapping and localization techniques[9]. Through the application of SLAM algorithms, the robot is able to construct a three-dimensional representation of the environment while simultaneously estimating its own position[10]. This capability allows the robot to move safely and efficiently within complex indoor or semi-enclosed construction environments.

Second, the system performs automated construction waste detection using computer vision and deep learning methods[11]. Visual data captured by RGB-D cameras are processed using object detection algorithms to identify different types of waste materials present in the environment[12]. By combining image information with depth measurements, the system can estimate the three-dimensional location of detected objects[13]. This information is essential for subsequent robotic manipulation tasks.

Third, the robotic platform integrates a lightweight robotic arm equipped with a multi-degree-of-freedom manipulator to perform object grasping and

handling[4]. After a target object is detected and localized, the system calculates a suitable grasping trajectory and executes the manipulation task. This capability enables the robot to physically interact with waste materials and supports automated sorting and handling operations within the construction site.

The main objective of this demonstration is to evaluate the feasibility of applying robotic perception, navigation, and manipulation technologies to real construction environments[2]. Specifically, the project aims to investigate whether autonomous robotic systems can improve the efficiency of construction waste assessment and reduce the reliance on manual inspection and sorting processes. By integrating sensing, artificial intelligence, and robotic manipulation capabilities, the system seeks to provide a practical technological solution for automated waste monitoring and management.

This demonstration is closely aligned with the broader objectives of the REINCARNATE project, which aims to promote circular economy principles within the construction sector. The project seeks to maximize the lifecycle value of buildings, construction products, and materials while significantly reducing the amount of construction and demolition waste. By developing innovative technologies and digital solutions for waste monitoring, material tracking, and circular resource management, REINCARNATE aims to support a more sustainable and resource-efficient construction industry.

The robotic system developed in this demonstration contributes to several REINCARNATE impact pathways (I1–I18). From a scientific perspective, the system advances research on robotic perception, autonomous navigation, and intelligent manipulation in complex construction environments. The integration of multi-modal sensing technologies and AI-based object recognition algorithms contributes to the development of digital construction monitoring tools and supports the creation of data-driven construction management systems[7].

Figure 3. Robotics system

From a societal perspective, the adoption of robotic technologies in construction waste management can improve safety conditions on construction sites. By reducing the need for manual waste inspection and handling, the system helps minimize worker exposure to hazardous materials and physically demanding tasks[5]. In addition, the demonstration raises awareness of the importance of digitalization and automation in promoting sustainable construction practices.

From a techno-economic perspective, the system demonstrates the potential for automated waste assessment and sorting solutions that support circular material value chains. By enabling more efficient identification and separation

of recyclable materials, robotic technologies can help increase the recovery rate of construction materials and reduce the costs associated with waste transportation and disposal[1]. These improvements contribute to the long-term goal of establishing a circular construction economy in which materials are reused, recycled, and reintegrated into new construction projects.

In summary, this demonstration illustrates how autonomous robotic technologies can support the digital transformation of construction waste management. By combining environmental perception, artificial intelligence, and robotic manipulation, the system provides a practical approach to improving waste monitoring, material recovery, and circular resource management in modern construction environments.

A contextual photograph of the construction site environment is included to illustrate the semi-structured conditions in which the robotic system is deployed. Such environments typically contain unfinished structures, temporary equipment, construction materials, and waste debris, presenting a challenging yet realistic scenario for evaluating robotic perception and manipulation capabilities.

3. Innovation description

3.1 Overall framework of the robotic system

The autonomous robotic system is organized into six functional modules that facilitate a seamless workflow from environmental perception to task execution. The workflow of the framework is structured as follows (shown in figure 1):

- (1) Perception and Localization (Stereo Vision & Waste Spatial Localization): The system initiates with the Stereo Vision module, where raw data from a stereo camera undergoes image rectification and stereo matching to generate a high-fidelity 3D Point Cloud[14]. Simultaneously, the Waste Spatial Localization module performs real-time waste recognition[6]. By

fusing semantic recognition with the point cloud data through a filtering process, the system precisely sends localized target coordinates to the subsequent modules.

- (2) Action Execution (Waste Picking and Disposal): Once target information is extracted, the Waste Picking and Disposal module takes command. This involves a coordinated execution between the robotic arm for trajectory reaching and the end effector for the final grasping and sorting of the identified construction waste.
- (3) Mission Planning (Path Planning & Target Selection): For site-wide operations, the Path Planning module utilizes a map service to implement an Internal Spiral Full-coverage Path Planning algorithm, ensuring the robot traverses the entire designated area[15]. The Target Selection module then acts as a decision-maker; it receives path points and evaluates them based on a distance threshold and occupancy probability to determine the optimal sequence for waste collection.
- (4) Motion Control (Local Navigation): The final layer, Local Navigation, ensures operational safety[16]. It continuously monitors for obstacles within a circular safety zone. If an obstacle is detected, Local Path Planning is triggered to bypass the threat; otherwise, the system adheres to the Global Path Planning and directs the mobile base to execute the movement.

Figure 4. Overall workflow

3.2 Hardware architecture design

This section details the physical realization of the proposed robotic system. The hardware architecture is designed with a hierarchical “Decision-Execution” topology, integrating a robust mobile platform, a high-precision manipulation module, and a multi-modal perception suite.

3.2.1 Mechatronic Architecture Overview

The system consists of four integrated subsystems: the Mobile Execution Unit, the Manipulation Unit, the Perception Unit, and the Central Decision Unit. The architecture distinguishes between high-level computation and real-time

control. The Upper Decision Unit (ROS Host) handles computationally intensive tasks such as SLAM and visual recognition[17], while the Bottom Execution Unit (STM32 Microcontroller) manages high-frequency motor control and sensor data acquisition.

Figure 5. Robot hardware system schema

3.2.2 Mobile Platform and Drive System

The mobile base is a differential-drive chassis designed for efficient locomotion on flat and semi-structured surfaces[15] (as shown in figure 3).

Figure 6. Mobile platform

Figure 7. Embedded controller

(1) Chassis structure: The platform utilizes a rigid aluminum alloy chassis without active suspension. To compensate for minor terrain irregularities and minimize high-frequency vibrations transferring to the sensors, the chassis is equipped with 8-inch pneumatic off-road tires, which provide passive damping through tire deformation.

(2) Actuation system: Two brushless DC motors coupled with planetary gearboxes provide the driving force. The motors are controlled by a D50A Dual-Channel Motor Driver, which amplifies the low-voltage control signals from the microcontroller. This driver features optocoupler isolation to protect the

control circuit from electromagnetic interference (EMI) generated during motor operation.

(3) Embedded controller: An STM32F4 series microcontroller serves as the core of the execution layer[4]. It acts as the kinematic solver, parsing velocity commands and executing PID closed-loop control to ensure precise wheel rotation.

3.2.3 Manipulator and End-effector

The manipulation module features a lightweight 6-DOF robotic arm integrated with the mobile base[4], optimized for dexterity rather than heavy lifting.

Figure 8. Robotic arm

(1) Arm specifications: The arm has a maximum payload of 2kg and a reach of approximately 600mm[4]. It is driven by high-precision serial bus servos, allowing for accurate joint positioning (0.2° repeatability) essential for grasping small waste objects.

(2) Control interface: The STM32 controller acts as a communication bridge, forwarding high-level coordinate commands from the ROS host to the arm's internal trajectory planner via a UART serial interface.

(3) End-effector: A custom parallel-jaw gripper is utilized to grasp objects[7]. A wrist-mounted 6-axis Force/Torque sensor is integrated to provide tactile feedback, enabling the system to detect contact forces and verify successful grasping.

3.2.4 Power and Electrical System

To ensure the stable operation of the multi-voltage components, a centralized Power Management System is implemented.

Figure 9. Robot hardware connection logic diagram

(1) Energy storage: The system is powered by a 24V LiFePO4 battery pack, selected for its stable discharge plateau and safety profile.

(2) Voltage transformation: Since the ROS host, LiDAR (12V), and STM32 controller (5V) have distinct voltage requirements, a dedicated Voltage Transformation Module (DC-DC Converter) is employed. This module regulates the raw battery voltage into stable output rails, preventing over-voltage damage to sensitive sensors.

3.3 Algorithmic Approach for Assessment and Separation

This chapter describes the algorithmic methodologies implemented to achieve autonomous waste assessment and separation. The software architecture is built upon the ROS 1 (Robot Operating System) framework, adopting a strictly decoupled “Decision-Execution” topology[17]. This design ensures that

high-level cognitive tasks do not interfere with the real-time determinism required for motion control.

Figure 10. Overall architecture diagram of software system

3.3.1 Hierarchical Software Architecture

The system's intelligence is distributed across two processing units: the Upper Decision Unit (ROS Host) and the Bottom Execution Unit (STM32). The software stack is organized into three functional layers:

(1) Perception & decision layer (ROS Host): Running on Ubuntu, this layer hosts the ROS Master node, which manages communication between distributed nodes. It handles complex data processing, including SLAM (Gmapping/Cartographer), neural network inference, and the move_base navigation stack[15,18].

(2) Communication interface: A serialized data link connects the two units. The ROS host runs a dedicated Serial Driver Node that converts ROS topics

(/cmd_vel) into raw byte frames. The STM32 provides high-frequency feedback (50Hz) containing fused odometry and IMU data.

Figure 11. ROS communication mechanism

(3) Real-time execution layer (STM32): Handles the kinematic resolution, PID motor control, and sensor signal acquisition, ensuring safety and precision at the hardware level.

3.3.2 Kinematic Analysis and Adaptive Navigation

To navigate the semi-structured environment effectively, the system employs a hybrid navigation strategy within the standard move_base framework[16].

Figure 12. Workflow chart of full coverage path planning, navigation and obstacle avoidance

3.3.2.1 Coverage Path Planning

Unlike traditional point-to-point transport, waste assessment requires the robot to traverse the entire workspace. A Boustrophedon Cellular Decomposition global planner plugin is integrated into move_base to generate a coverage path[15]. The workspace is divided into linear cells, and the robot scans each cell sequentially to ensure 100% area coverage.

Figure 13. Navigation framework

3.3.2.2 Kinematic Resolution

The motion control relies on the precise translation of task-space commands into joint-space actuation[4].

(1) Inverse kinematics (execution level): The STM32 controller receives the target linear velocity v and angular velocity ω from the local planner (e.g., `teb_local_planner`). It computes the required rotational speeds for the left (v_L) and right (v_R) wheels using the differential drive model:

$$v_L = v - \frac{\omega W}{2}, v_R = v + \frac{\omega W}{2}$$

where W is the wheel track. These target speeds are maintained via a dual-loop PID controller.

(2) Forward kinematics (Odom generation): To close the localization loop, the STM32 computes the robot's real-time displacement (x, y, θ) by integrating the encoder feedback and 9-axis IMU data. This fused odometry is published to the ROS `/odom` topic and broadcast via the `tf` (Transform) tree to correct the SLAM algorithm's drift[19,20].

3.3.3 Waste detection

To ensure real-time performance on the embedded computing unit, the assessment pipeline abandons computationally expensive semantic segmentation networks[21]. Instead, it adopts a high-efficiency “Detection-Projection-Estimation” workflow to generate 3D Oriented Bounding Boxes (OBB) directly from RGB-D data[11].

Figure 14. Workflow chart of waste identification, positioning and pickup

Step 1: High-speed visual detection (2D)

The RGB stream is processed by a YOLOv8 node optimized with TensorRT[3]. This model is trained to detect waste categories and outputs 2D bounding boxes u,v,w,h in the pixel coordinate system. This stage effectively filters out background noise and isolates the Region of Interest (ROI).

Step 2: Lightweight 3D bounding box estimation

Instead of processing the entire point cloud, the system employs a Frustum-based 3D Estimation method:

Depth projection: The 2D ROI is projected into 3D space using the camera's intrinsic matrix and aligned depth map, creating a frustum point cloud[4,12,13].

Outlier removal: A Statistical Outlier Removal (SOR) filter is applied to eliminate noise points caused by sensor edge artifacts.

OBB generation: The system computes the Oriented Bounding Box (OBB) of the filtered cluster using Principal Component Analysis (PCA). This rapidly calculates the object's 3D centroid x,y,z and its principal geometric axes (orientation), providing the necessary pose for the gripper without heavy neural network inference.

Step 3: Spectral material verification

Once the 3D box is defined, the robotic arm moves the spectrometer probe to the calculated centroid coordinates. The spectral data (900-1700nm) is captured and analyzed by a 1D-CNN classifier. This step validates the material properties (e.g., differentiating PET plastic from glass), ensuring the separation decision is based on physicochemical properties rather than just visual appearance.

3.3.4 Feedback-Driven Manipulation Strategy

The manipulation strategy relies on the 3D OBB generated in the previous stage to execute robust grasping within the ROS `move_base` and `moveit` (or custom kinematic) context.

(1) Grasp pose generation: Instead of complex grasp synthesis networks, the system derives the grasp pose directly from the OBB's minor axis (the shortest dimension of the box)[4], which typically corresponds to the optimal gripping width for waste objects like bottles or cans. The approach vector is aligned with the box's surface normal.

(2) Force-adaptive execution with recovery: The execution relies on a Finite State Machine (FSM)[22]:

Contact Detection: The arm advances until the Force/Torque sensor detects a contact threshold (e.g., 2N) or the grasp center is reached.

Slip-aware grasping: The gripper closes. If the motor current feedback indicates a stall before the expected object width is reached (rigid object) or if the F/T sensor detects micro-vibrations (slip), the clamping force is dynamically adjusted via the STM32 execution layer.

Collision recovery: If the servo current spikes before the grasp pose is reached, indicating an unintended collision, the arm immediately retracts and triggers a re-planning routine to approach the object from a different vector.

4. Demonstration Setup

4.1 Demonstration site

The demonstration of the proposed robotic construction waste assessment system was conducted at the Longhu Binjiang Tianjie construction project located in Wuhan, China. This project represents a large-scale urban development site where multiple buildings are under construction simultaneously. The construction environment is characterized by unfinished concrete structures, temporary working areas, and the presence of construction materials and debris generated during different stages of building development.

The selected demonstration area consists of partially completed building floors where structural elements such as reinforced concrete columns, beams, and slabs have already been installed. However, interior finishing work has not yet been completed, resulting in open and semi-structured spaces that contain construction materials, equipment, and occasional debris. These conditions provide a realistic testing environment for evaluating the capabilities of autonomous robotic systems designed for construction waste monitoring and handling.

Figure 15. Site Conditions of the Project

Such semi-structured construction environments present several challenges for robotic operation[2,23]. The spatial layout may change over time as construction progresses, temporary materials may be placed in different locations, and lighting conditions may vary depending on the openness of the structure. Therefore, the site provides a representative scenario for testing robotic perception, mapping, navigation, and manipulation capabilities in real-world construction environments.

4.2 Deployment environment

The robotic system was deployed in several indoor construction areas within the building structure where construction activities were ongoing but the structural framework had already been completed. These areas typically consist of large open floor spaces with reinforced concrete columns, exposed beams, and unfinished walls. The floor surfaces are mainly composed of raw concrete, and various construction materials may be temporarily stored in the workspace[14]. In addition to structural components, the environment contains stacks of building blocks, packaging materials, wooden boards, plastic sheets, and other construction-related materials. These elements create a cluttered environment

in which the robotic platform must navigate safely while maintaining awareness of surrounding obstacles. Such conditions provide a realistic testbed for evaluating the robustness of autonomous navigation and obstacle avoidance algorithm

Figure 16. Site Conditions of the project

Lighting conditions inside the building are primarily influenced by natural daylight entering through open wall sections and window spaces. As a result, illumination levels may vary significantly across different parts of the workspace. These lighting variations present additional challenges for vision-based perception systems, particularly when detecting small or partially occluded waste objects.

4.3 Robotic system deployment

The robotic system deployed in this demonstration consists of a mobile robotic platform equipped with a lightweight robotic arm and multiple perception sensors. The mobile base enables the robot to move autonomously across the construction site, while the robotic manipulator allows the system to physically interact with construction materials and waste objects.

The perception system integrates multiple sensing modalities, including LiDAR sensors for spatial mapping and localization, as well as RGB-D cameras for visual perception and depth measurement[24]. By combining data from these sensors, the robotic system is able to construct a three-dimensional

representation of the surrounding environment while simultaneously detecting objects located within the workspace.

The operational workflow of the robotic system follows several sequential stages. First, the robot performs environmental perception and mapping using LiDAR-based SLAM algorithms, allowing the system to generate a spatial map of the construction site and determine its own position within the environment[25]. Second, the visual perception system analyzes camera images using deep learning algorithms to detect construction waste materials such as concrete fragments, bricks, wood pieces, plastic packaging, and metal components[6].

Once an object has been detected, the system estimates its three-dimensional position using depth information obtained from the RGB-D camera[13]. This spatial information is then used to plan a grasping trajectory for the robotic arm. Finally, the manipulator executes the grasping motion to pick up or manipulate the target object. Through this integrated perception–planning–manipulation pipeline, the robotic platform is capable of performing automated inspection and handling of construction waste materials.

4.4 Data collection

During the demonstration experiments, multiple types of sensor data were collected to support robotic perception, system evaluation, and algorithm development. The primary data sources include LiDAR sensors, RGB cameras, depth sensors, and internal system logs generated by the robotic platform.

LiDAR sensors continuously generate three-dimensional point cloud data representing the geometry of the surrounding environment[26]. These point clouds are used by the SLAM algorithm to construct spatial maps and support real-time localization of the robot. In addition to LiDAR data, RGB cameras capture visual images of the construction environment, which are used for object detection and classification using deep learning algorithms[3].

Depth cameras provide additional information about the distance between the robot and surrounding objects. By combining RGB image data with depth measurements, the system is able to estimate the three-dimensional coordinates of detected objects[11]. This information is essential for enabling precise robotic grasping and manipulation operations.

Figure 17. A house with construction debris

Operational data from the robotic system, including navigation trajectories, detection results, and manipulation commands, were also recorded during the experiments. These logs allow researchers to analyze the performance of the system and evaluate the effectiveness of different perception and control algorithms under realistic construction site conditions.

4.5 System platform architecture

In addition to the robotic sensing and manipulation components deployed on the construction site, a digital monitoring and management platform was developed to support the overall operation of the construction waste assessment system. This platform provides a centralized interface for visualizing site information, monitoring environmental conditions, and managing waste cleaning tasks. By combining robotic perception data with a digital construction monitoring system, the platform enables more efficient supervision of construction waste conditions and improves the coordination of waste management activities on site.

The system platform integrates several functional modules, including construction monitoring dashboards, BIM-based model management, and task management interfaces. The construction monitoring dashboard provides a high-level overview of the project status, displaying information such as construction progress, spatial layout of the site, and operational indicators. Through a digital visualization interface, site managers can observe the distribution of construction areas and identify zones where construction waste may accumulate. The platform can visually highlight areas where cleaning has not yet been completed, allowing managers to quickly understand the waste status across different parts of the construction site.

Figure 18. BIM-based Management Platform

In addition to the monitoring dashboard, the platform also incorporates a BIM-based model management interface. By integrating the digital building model with construction site information, the system allows users to interact with the 3D representation of the building structure. Different floors, construction zones, and structural components can be inspected within the model environment. This digital representation provides spatial context for waste monitoring and helps managers understand where waste materials are located within the building structure.

One important function of the platform is the ability to distinguish whether construction waste has already been cleared from specific areas. The system analyzes visual and spatial information collected by the robotic sensing system and compares the detected conditions with predefined site management rules. Based on this information, the platform can determine whether waste materials remain in a particular location. If waste accumulation is detected, the system can automatically generate cleaning tasks and assign them to relevant site management personnel.

Figure 19. BIM-based Management Platform

The task management module enables site managers to track waste cleaning operations and ensure that necessary actions are carried out. Once a cleaning task is generated, the platform records the task status, including pending tasks, tasks in progress, and completed tasks. This mechanism helps improve the transparency and efficiency of construction waste management, ensuring that waste removal activities are systematically monitored and documented.

Overall, the system platform demonstrates how digital monitoring technologies can support more intelligent management of construction waste on building sites. By integrating robotic sensing data with visual monitoring interfaces and task management tools, the platform provides a structured approach for

supervising waste conditions and coordinating cleaning activities. This framework not only improves operational efficiency but also contributes to more organized and sustainable construction site management practices.

Figure 20. Construction Monitoring Dashboard

5. Results and Innovation

KPI	Baseline	Result	Unit	Impact ID
Construction and Demolition Waste (CDW) Reduction	Conventional construction waste management relying on manual inspection and limited on-site sorting	≥80	%	I8
Reusability Increase	Low recovery of reusable materials due to mixed waste streams	≥70	%	I14

Emission Reduction	High emissions caused by waste transport and landfill disposal	≥70	%	I7
Operational Cost Reduction Potential	High operational cost associated with manual waste inspection and sorting	≥10	%	I13
Worker Safety Improvement	Manual handling of construction waste in hazardous environments	Reduced exposure to hazardous tasks	qualitative	I17

6. Contribution to Impacts

The demonstration of the autonomous robotic system for on-site construction waste assessment and sorting contributes to multiple impact pathways defined within the REINCARNATE project. By integrating robotic perception, autonomous navigation, intelligent object recognition, and robotic manipulation into a unified system, the case study provides both technological and practical evidence of how digital and automated solutions can improve circular construction practices.

A central contribution of this demonstration lies in the digitalization of construction waste monitoring. The robotic system continuously collects structured data from the construction environment, including LiDAR-based spatial information, RGB-D image data, object detection results, and operational records generated during navigation and manipulation. These data provide a digital representation of waste materials present on site and create the basis for more accurate monitoring, documentation, and evaluation of material flows

during construction activities. In this sense, the demonstration supports REINCARNATE impacts related to digital tools, data integration, and lifecycle-oriented construction management.

The case study also contributes to the transition from conventional waste handling to circular material management[1]. In traditional construction practice, waste materials are often mixed, manually inspected, and transported for off-site treatment, which reduces the potential for direct reuse or high-quality recycling. In contrast, the demonstrated robotic system improves the early-stage identification and separation of materials such as concrete, bricks, wood, plastics, and metals[7]. By enabling more precise detection and on-site assessment, the system increases the possibility of identifying recyclable or reusable materials before they become part of mixed waste streams. This directly supports REINCARNATE objectives related to improved material recovery, increased reusability, and reduced waste generation.

From a scientific and technological perspective, the demonstration provides evidence that advanced robotic technologies can be applied in semi-structured construction environments. The integration of LiDAR-based mapping, RGB-D sensing, YOLO-based visual detection, and robotic grasp planning shows how multiple digital technologies can be combined to perform automated construction waste assessment tasks[27]. The case therefore contributes to the advancement of robotics and artificial intelligence applications in the construction sector, supporting innovation in intelligent site monitoring and automated material handling.

The demonstration further contributes to safer and more sustainable construction operations. Construction waste sorting is traditionally performed manually, often exposing workers to dust, sharp materials, unstable debris, and repetitive physical labor[5]. By introducing autonomous robotic inspection and handling, the system reduces the need for direct human involvement in hazardous waste sorting tasks. This contributes to improved occupational safety and better working conditions while also supporting broader sustainability

goals through more efficient waste separation and reduced transportation requirements.

Another important contribution is the generation of interoperable digital information that can be linked with the Circular Potential Information Model (CP-IM) and other REINCARNATE digital platforms. The ability to associate identified waste categories, location information, and handling records with digital material tracking systems creates value beyond the immediate demonstration itself. It supports the development of traceable and reusable datasets that can be used for future material passports, digital waste inventories, and circular decision-support systems. In this way, the demonstration not only validates a robotic system in practice, but also contributes to the wider digital ecosystem envisioned by REINCARNATE.

Overall, this demonstration supports REINCARNATE impacts across scientific, societal, and techno-economic dimensions. Scientifically, it advances knowledge on robotic perception, autonomous navigation, and intelligent construction site automation. The integration of LiDAR-based mapping, RGB-D sensing, and deep learning-based object detection shows how multi-modal sensing technologies can be applied in semi-structured construction environments. These results contribute to intelligent monitoring systems capable of collecting structured data on construction materials and waste streams, supporting further research on digital construction management and automated material handling.

From a societal perspective, the system helps improve safety and working conditions on construction sites. Traditional construction waste sorting often requires workers to manually inspect and handle mixed debris, including sharp objects, heavy materials, and dust. By introducing autonomous robotic inspection and manipulation, the system reduces direct human interaction with hazardous waste materials and promotes awareness of digital and circular construction practices.

From a techno-economic perspective, the robotic system supports more efficient waste sorting and material recovery. By enabling earlier identification and classification of recyclable materials, it increases the potential for reuse and recycling of construction components such as concrete, wood, metal, and plastics. This improved sorting capability reduces the volume of mixed waste sent to landfill and lowers environmental impacts associated with waste transport and disposal. Integration with digital platforms such as the Circular Potential Information Model (CP-IM) also supports data-driven decision making and lifecycle material tracking in circular construction.

Although the current prototype represents a demonstration-stage system, the results indicate strong potential for further development, scaling, and integration into future circular construction workflows. With continued technological improvements in perception accuracy, robotic manipulation, and system robustness, such autonomous systems could become an important component of next-generation digital construction sites. In the long term, the adoption of robotic waste assessment technologies may contribute to more efficient resource utilization, reduced environmental impacts, and the broader implementation of circular economy principles within the construction industry.

Impact ID	Impact Description	Contribution of the Demonstration
I1	Digitisation methods for building information	Robotic sensing and perception generate digital data describing construction waste materials and site conditions.
I3	AI-based valuation and planning	AI-based object detection methods support automated identification and assessment of construction waste materials.

14	Robotics-supported automation solutions	The autonomous robotic system enables automated inspection, detection, and handling of construction waste on site.
16	Scientific case studies of circular construction practices	The Wuhan demonstration provides a real-world experimental case study of robotic construction waste assessment.
17	CO ₂ reduction in the construction industry	Improved recycling and waste separation reduce emissions associated with waste transport and landfill disposal.
18	Elimination of construction waste and environmental impact reduction	Automated waste detection and sorting improve material recovery and reduce mixed waste generation.
113	Cost reduction for large construction companies	Automation of waste monitoring and sorting reduces operational costs associated with manual waste management.
114	Cost reduction for small construction companies	Improved material reuse and recycling increase economic efficiency of construction waste management.
117	Reduction of fatal work injuries	Robotic automation reduces hazardous manual waste inspection and handling tasks on construction sites.

7. Replication and Next Steps

The demonstration of the autonomous robotic system for construction waste assessment and sorting provides valuable insights into the potential application of robotic technologies within real construction environments. Through the deployment of the system in a semi-structured construction site, the project was able to evaluate not only the technical performance of the robotic platform but also the operational feasibility of integrating such systems into existing construction workflows. The results obtained from the demonstration highlight several important lessons related to sensing reliability, system adaptability, and the broader requirements for large-scale adoption of robotic waste management technologies.

One important lesson learned from the demonstration is the effectiveness of combining multiple sensing technologies to improve perception accuracy in complex construction environments. The integration of LiDAR-based mapping, RGB-D visual sensing, and deep learning-based object detection enables the robotic system to collect detailed spatial and visual information about the surrounding environment[28]. This multi-modal perception approach significantly improves the system's ability to identify and locate construction waste materials such as concrete fragments, bricks, wood pieces, plastics, and metal components. However, the experiments also showed that environmental conditions such as dust, uneven lighting, and partial occlusion of objects can still affect detection performance[29]. These findings suggest that future research should continue to improve sensor fusion methods and machine learning models to ensure reliable operation in highly dynamic construction sites[30].

Another important lesson concerns the adaptability of robotic systems in environments that are continuously changing. Construction sites are inherently dynamic spaces where materials, equipment, and temporary structures are frequently moved or rearranged. As a result, robotic systems operating in such environments must be capable of continuously updating their understanding of

the surrounding space. The use of SLAM-based mapping and localization techniques proved to be highly beneficial in this demonstration, allowing the robotic platform to generate and update spatial maps of the environment while navigating through the site[31]. Nevertheless, further improvements in navigation planning and obstacle avoidance algorithms will be necessary to support long-term autonomous operation in large and crowded construction environments[32].

From the perspective of replication, the technological framework developed in this demonstration has strong potential for application in other construction projects[8]. Many construction environments share common characteristics, including semi-structured spaces, heterogeneous material distributions, and temporary obstacles. The modular architecture of the proposed robotic system—including the mobile base, perception sensors, and robotic manipulator—allows the system to be adapted to different construction scenarios with relatively minor modifications[2]. For example, similar robotic systems could be deployed in building renovation projects, demolition sites, infrastructure construction environments, or indoor industrial environments where material identification and sorting tasks are required.

Furthermore, the digital data generated by the robotic system provides opportunities for integration with broader digital construction ecosystems. During operation, the robot collects large volumes of structured information, including spatial maps, visual images, detection results, and manipulation records. These data can be linked with digital construction platforms such as the Circular Potential Information Model (CP-IM), allowing construction stakeholders to monitor material flows and track waste generation throughout the building lifecycle. The ability to generate such digital records can support data-driven decision making and enable more effective planning of recycling and reuse strategies.

Despite the promising results obtained in this demonstration, several challenges remain before large-scale deployment can be achieved. One of the primary

barriers relates to the cost and complexity of robotic hardware systems. Mobile robots equipped with multiple sensors and robotic manipulators require significant investment in both hardware and maintenance. Additionally, the successful deployment of such systems requires reliable integration with existing construction management processes and digital infrastructure. Construction companies may also need to adapt their operational workflows to accommodate robotic inspection and sorting processes.

Another potential barrier is the requirement for system robustness in harsh construction environments[33] or improvements in perception algorithms and dataset development will be necessary to increase the accuracy of waste detection and material classification across a broader range of construction materials. Dust, vibration, temperature variations, and uneven surfaces can affect the reliability of sensors and mechanical components. Ensuring that robotic platforms can maintain stable performance under these conditions will be an important consideration for future system development. Furthermore, the introduction of robotic technologies into construction sites may require additional training for construction workers and site managers to ensure safe and effective collaboration between humans and robotic systems.

Looking ahead, several directions for future work have been identified. First, further improvements in perception algorithms and dataset development will be necessary to increase the accuracy of waste detection and material classification across a broader range of construction materials[34]. Second, enhancements in robotic manipulation capabilities will allow the system to handle heavier objects and more irregular shapes commonly encountered in construction waste. Third, deeper integration with digital construction platforms and circular economy tools will enable more comprehensive monitoring of material flows and support decision-making related to material reuse and recycling.

Future research may also explore the integration of additional sensing technologies such as hyperspectral imaging or advanced 3D scanning to further

improve material identification accuracy[35]. In addition, collaborative robotic systems involving multiple robots working together could significantly increase the efficiency of waste inspection and sorting tasks on large construction sites[36].

In summary, the demonstration confirms that autonomous robotic systems have strong potential to support more sustainable and efficient construction waste management practices[2]. While several technological and operational challenges remain, continued research and development, combined with stronger integration with digital construction platforms, will enable these systems to play an increasingly important role in future circular construction ecosystems.

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